

K/ha, and 18 kg S/ha.

Urea to 100 kg N/ha was added with the 17:17:17 mixture and with DAP. Muriate of potash at 42 kg K/ha was applied for all treatments. Gypsum,

elemental S, and calcium oxide were applied basally.

Urea at 100 kg N/ha plus gypsum at 1/2 t/ha overwhelmingly increased yield (see table). Gypsum at 1/2 t/ha with

17:17:17 mixture and DAP equaled urea at 100 kg N/ha plus gypsum at 1/4 t/ha. S enhanced yield more than Ca. Gypsum is an easily available and cheaper source of S than elemental S. □

Efficiency of phosphorus form combined with organic manure in rice - rice cropping

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We compared direct and residual effects of phosphate rock and superphosphate on IR20 in 1982-83 kharif (wet season) and rabi (dry season). Treatments were imposed on the kharif crop, residual effects were studied on the rabi crop in a randomized block design replicated three times.

Both crops received 100 kg N and 42 kg K/ha. Soil was clay loam, with 220 kg available N/ha, 4.3 kg P/ha, 271 kg available K/ha, and pH 8.0. Organic manures were farmyard manure

Grain yield and return of phosphate and organic manure combinations. Coimbatore, India, 1982-83.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Return ^a / \$ invested
	Kharif	Rabi	
Farmyard manure alone	4.7	4.7	1.87
Farmyard manure + superphosphate	5.4	5.0	2.06
Farmyard manure + rock phosphate	4.9	5.4	2.10
Compost alone	4.7	4.8	1.98
Compost + superphosphate	5.6	4.6	2.03
Compost + rock phosphate	5.2	5.0	2.12
Greenleaf manure alone	5.9	4.8	1.93
Green leaf + superphosphate	5.9	4.9	2.09
Green leaf + rock phosphate	5.0	5.3	2.03
Superphosphate alone	5.4	4.9	2.10
Rock phosphate alone	4.4	4.9	1.90
Control (no Organic manure)	4.0	4.0	1.54
CD (0.05)	0.1	0.5	

^a Av of 2 seasons.

(FYM) — 0.05% N, 0.11% P, 0.42% K; composted water hyacinth — 1.5% N, 0.34% P, 1.25% K; and leucaena green leaf manure — 3.0% N, 1.7% P, 2.08% K.

The efficiency of superphosphate and rock phosphate improved when they were combined with organic manures (see table). Superphosphate applied with organic manure had highest direct effect. Superphosphate with leucaena green leaf

manure was best. Rock phosphate efficiency improved with composted water hyacinth.

Residual effects of all organic manures and P were equal. Rock phosphate with organic manure was better in obtaining high grain yield. FYM was the best in improving rock phosphate efficiency. Composted water hyacinth with rock phosphate gave the highest net return. □

Effect of Azospirillum on ASD16 rice

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We evaluated the effect of *Azospirillum* on grain yield of ASD16 (110 d duration) Jun-Oct 1986. Five N levels (0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha) and 4

Azospirillum treatments (control, seed treatment, seedling dip, and field application) were examined in a split-plot design with 3 replications. Available NPK was 298-75-164 kg/ha.

Yield differences due to *Azospirillum* treatment as well as the interaction between *Azospirillum* and N levels were not significant. All four N treatments were significantly superior to the control. □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Rice-based fish and vegetable cropping system in coastal saline soils

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In the coastal saline soils of the Sundarbans, rice is grown only during the monsoon season. No crop is grown during the winter and summer seasons because good quality irrigation water is lacking and soil salinity is high. Saline water is plentiful throughout the year.

Yield and income with different rice - fish - vegetable cropping systems in Barrackpore, India, 1982-85.

Cropping pattern	Yield (t/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Rice	3.4	398.00	150.00
Rice + freshwater fish	3.4	855.30	395.30
Rice - brackish water fish	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	3.4	1297.60	624.60
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	3.4	1754.90	869.90
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	3.4	2594.30	1294.30
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish + vegetables	10.7		

We conducted inter-institute collaborative trials for 4 yr to expand land use through rice - fish culture followed by brackish water fish culture with vegetable cultivation on the bunds. (The vegetable crop was grown only in 1985.)

Freshwater fish (carp and

Macrobranchium rosenbergil) with rice during the monsoon season approximately doubled returns (see table). Brackish water fish (*P. monodon* and *L. parasia*) during the fallow period increased gross income four times. Rice and freshwater fish during the monsoon and brackish water fish during the

fallow increased returns five times. Vegetable crops along the field borders with rice and freshwater fish followed by brackish water fish increased income eight times.

It was possible to get 2 fish crops, 1 rice crop, and 1 vegetable crop in 1 yr from 1 field by judicious land use. □

Transplanted aman - potato - maize cropping pattern in Bangladesh

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We studied a transplanted aman rice - potato - maize cropping pattern for 2 yr in farmers' fields at 3 sites in Chittagong District and compared it with farmers' cropping patterns. The cropping pattern was replicated on five farms in partially irrigated uplands.

In the improved cropping pattern, maize variety Sadaf was introduced as an alternate crop to broadcast local aus variety Chinnal, potato variety Cardinal as an alternate to the farmers' local variety, and transplanted aman variety BRII to Pajam. The fields were fertilized with 80-60-40 kg NPK/ha for

Yield^a of transplanted aman - potato - maize cropping pattern at 3 sites in Bangladesh, 1983-85.

Crop	Yield (t/ha)				CV (%)	Material cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
	Patiya	Satkania	Fatikchari	Mean			
<i>Farmers' pattern</i>							
Transplanted aman	2.4	2.4	2.5	2.4	1.6	89	258
Potato	8.2	7.7	5.5	7.1	16.2	219	323
Broadcast aus	2.0	1.9	2.0	2.0	1.1	42	209
<i>Improved pattern</i>							
Transplanted aman	4.0	4.0	4.1	4.0	1.7	102	429
Potato	21.6	25.4	21.6	24.9	10.0	491	1126
Maize	4.6	4.4	4.2	4.4	3.8	117	588

^a2-yr av.

transplanted aman, 120-100-100 kg NPK/ha for potato, and 100-60-40 kg NPK/ha for maize. Spacing was 25 × 15 cm for transplanted aman, 60 × 30 cm for potato, and 75 × 25 cm for maize. Seeding rate was 80 kg/ha for transplanted aman, 1,500 kg/ha for

potato, and 30 kg/ha for maize. All crops in all locations received normal cultural treatments.

Average yields for 2 yr are presented in the table. Net return for the improved pattern was 171% of the farmers' cropping pattern. □

Announcements

Two IRRI scientists awarded Japan's top science prize

Sharing the 1987 Japan Prize are Dr. Henry M. Beachell, former IRRI plant breeder, and Dr. Gurdev S. Khush, currently head of IRRI's Plant Breeding Department. The Prize — patterned “in the tradition of the Nobel Prize” — is Japan's most prestigious.

The award was given 14 Apr in Tokyo in the presence of Japan's Crown Prince Akihito and Crown Princess Michiko, Prime Minister Yasuhiro Nakasone, and foreign dignitaries. On 15 Apr, Emperor Hirohito received the rice scientists at the Imperial Palace.

Beachell, who joined IRRI in 1963,

was honored for his work on IR8, the first semidwarf rice variety to be widely grown in the tropics. Khush, who joined IRRI in 1967, led the effort that developed IR36, which became the most widely grown variety — of any crop — the world has ever known. By 1983, IR36 was planted on 11 million ha in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

Beachell played a key role in the selection of IR8, which IRRI released in late 1966 from a cross of a dwarf rice from China with a vigorous Indonesian variety. IR8 had short, stiff straws that enabled it to yield heavily without falling over. Its insensitivity to daylength meant that farmers could grow it around the world.

With good management, IR8 yielded 4 or 5 t/ha on irrigated farms; traditional varieties yielded 1 or 2 t. The increased farm productivity that followed in the wake of IR8 gave rise to the term “Green Revolution.”

IR36 was developed under Khush's leadership from crosses involving 13 parents from 6 countries. It was evaluated cooperatively by scientists at IRRI and in national agricultural programs throughout Asia. IR36 was first named as a farm variety in 1976 in the Philippines, then released by national agencies across Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

The popularity of IR36 was due largely to its genetic resistance to a